

EXPLORING THE FUNCTIONS AND REASONS FOR INTER-SENTENTIAL CODE-SWITCHING AMONG LECTURERS

Noor Hanim Rahmat¹ⁱ,

Noor Ahnis Othman²,

Norseha Unin³

^{1,2}Akademi Pengajian Bahasa,
Universiti Teknologi MARA,
Shah Alam, Malaysia

³Akademi Pengajian Bahasa,
Universiti Teknologi MARA,
Cawangan Sarawak,
Kampus Samarahan, Malaysia

Abstract:

The two most common categories in the code switching are intra-sentential and inter-sentential. Intra-sentential code switching occurs when the speaker code switches within sentences. Inter-sentential code switching, on the other hand, refers to the mixing of two languages in two separate sentences in an utterance. This research investigates the use of inter-sentential code switching among lecturers of a public university in Malaysia, where English is mainly the medium of instruction for many core courses. The need to conduct this study is due to the lack of empirical evidences on the difference in code-switching among teachers across age, experience, and faculties. 85 lecturers from six faculties who teach in a public university participated in a quantitative survey. The findings of this study reveal the categories of code-switching used by the lecturers from different faculties, as well as the functions and reasons for the code-switching. Future studies should consider the need for a measurement of evaluating the functions and reasons of code-switching among the teachers and students.

Keywords: code switching, intra-sentential and inter-sentential, reasons for code switching

ⁱCorrespondence: email patanim@gmail.com, noorahnis@salam.uitm.edu.my, norseha@sarawak.uitm.edu

1. Introduction

Code switching is the use of two or more languages in the same conversation or utterance. While Poplack (2000) defines code-switching as the alternation of two languages within a single discourse, sentence or constituent, Clyne (2000) states that code-switching is the alternative use of two languages either within a sentence or between sentences. Intra-sentential and Inter-sentential are two common categories in the code switching literature. For example intra-sentential code switching for Malay and English occurs when someone uses Malay language whenever he or she cannot find an English word in one sentence. On the other hand, inter-sentential code switching refers to a mix of Malay and English language alternately from one sentence to another. According to other scholars, inter-sentential alternations occur when the switch is made across sentence boundaries (Grosjean, 1982; Torres, 1989).

1.1 Background of Study

Code switching among bilinguals of Malay and English language occurs when they cannot find the accurate word or when there is no appropriate translation for the word in English. In such a situation, they tend to switch or mix the two languages in the utterances. Bhatia and Ritchie (2004) explain the four reasons for code switching on the basis of who, what, when and where it occurs. Firstly, who are the participants? Bhatia and Ritchie (2004) argue that the participants' roles and relationships play a significant role in bilinguals' language choice, whether they code switch or not depends very much on with whom they talk to. Secondly, what is the topic, content, or situation? According to Bhatia and Ritchie (2004), situational factors, social groups, settings or topics can influence the pattern of code switching. For example, gender roles in traditional societies are clearly distinguished. Therefore, code switching in women is different from that in men. Thirdly, when does code switching occur? When bilinguals do not want to give a clear answer, they usually code switch. The other reason for code switching is to add an interjection or sentence filler. For example, Malaysians or Singaporeans usually put 'la' at the end of sentences (Tay, 1989) since their spoken language usually has a 'la' sound at the end of sentences.

Finally, the fourth reason for code switching is where it can occur and whether it is considered acceptable within the context of the dominant language. For example, in terms of language dominance, there is a general tendency for bilinguals to mix elements from their dominant language (Malay) when using their non-dominant language (English). Although code switching is usually more common during informal interpersonal interactions, including those that take place between family members in natural contexts (Zentella, 1999), it is not clear whether the functions and reasons for code switching among lecturers are consistent with the existing literature on code switching, especially with regard to their situational factors. Therefore, the focus of this study is shaped by the literature reviewed with regard to the functions and reasons for code switching.

1.2 Statement of Problem

In recent years, code switching in the Malaysian context have been studied with regard to teaching English (Chen & Maarof, 2017; Lee 2010), lecturers' and students' beliefs (Mokhtar, 2015), teacher discourse (Chen & Ting, 2011) and classroom instructions (Ahmad & Jusoff, 2009). Code switching may be a useful teaching tool in the ESL classroom (Chen & Maarof, 2017) to enhance students' understanding (Mokhtar, 2015) because teachers' code-switching can be an effective teaching strategy when dealing with low English proficient learners (Ahmad & Jusoff, 2009). Previous studies also have shown that code switching occurs in formal classroom settings (Kow, 2003; Then & Ting, 2009). However, the functions and reasons for code switching among lecturers are not evident in the existing literature for the Malaysian context. It was also reported that teachers of different age group use code-switch for different reasons. Also, the difference in code-switching across age and teaching experience of teachers is not clearly inherent. Additionally, the difference in code-switching among teachers across faculties is also unknown.

1.3 Research Objective

This study was conducted to investigate inter-sentential code switching among lecturers of a public university in Malaysia, where English is mainly the medium of instruction for many core courses at the university. The lack of empirical evidences on the difference in code-switching among teachers across age, experience, and faculties compels the need to conduct this study.

1.4 Research Questions

- 1) Is there any significant difference in code-switching across age and teaching experience of teachers?
- 2) Is there any significant difference in code-switching among teachers across faculties?
- 3) How do the categories of code-switching influence classroom communication?
- 4) How do the functions of code-switching influence classroom communication?
- 5) How to reasons for code-switching influence classroom communication?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This section discusses the types of code-switch and their functions. It also presents the reasons why lecturers code-switch.

2.2 Classroom Interaction/Communication

Code switching is not always a conscious process, especially when lecturers are using English as a medium of instruction for teaching other than English courses. There are three functions of teachers' code switching; topic switch, affective functions, and

repetitive functions (Mattson & Burenhult, 1999). Firstly, in topic switch, the teacher shifts English language to Malay when explaining a particular topic. By making use of code switching, as in topic switch, the students' attention is directed to the new knowledge. Secondly, for affective functions, code switching is used for creating a supportive language environment in the classroom. Affective function of code switching, in this case, is used by the teacher to express emotions and build rapport with the students. Finally, for the repetitive function, the teacher uses code switching in classroom settings to provide clarity in meanings. While the instruction is conducted in English, the teacher code switches to Malay in order to clarify meaning. Therefore, code switching serves as a tool for communicative purposes in the transference and for clarity in meaning.

2.3 Types of Code-Switching

There three main types of code-switch. The study by Rahmat, Arepin, Mohd Yunos, and Syed Abdul Rahman (2017) identified the first type of code-switch as inter-sentential. This type is also known as inter-utterance. This type refers to the language done by the same speaker between utterances. According to Inter-sentential switching is a type of code-switching that occurs in two different sentences in which the first sentence is in full primary language (L1) and then followed by the second sentence in full second language (L2). Inter-sentential switching occurs in two separate sentences in an utterance because the bilingual speaker lacks proper or equivalent lexical resource, wants to be understood better by the other party of similar language ability and wants to show belonging to a certain group (Mohamad Khalil and Mohd Shahril Firdaus, 2018). The next type is known as inter-sentential. It is sometimes known as intra-sentential. This type of code-switch happens when the speaker code-switch within sentences. The third type is supra sentential or unitary code-switch. This is when speakers switch either a segment or a single item of the utterance.

2.4 Reasons for Code-Switching

There are five functions of code-switch and they are referential, directive, expressive, phatic and metalinguistic. Firstly, in the case of referential code-switch, the speaker uses the mother tongue if he/she does not know the word in the target language. The speaker will also use referential code-switch when he/she feels the word will change its meaning if he/she substitutes it with the word in the target language. In the case of directive code-switch, the speaker uses the native language when he/she wants the other person to join the discussion or even when he/she does not want the other person to join the discussion. The speaker is said to use expressive code-switch when he/she wants to emphasize his/her feelings, and the speaker is said to use phatic when he/she wants to highlight important points or ideas. Finally, the speaker may also use metalinguistic functions.

2.5 Past Research

A study was conducted by Shartiely (2016) to examine the alternating use of English and Swahili in classroom communication among lecturers in the University of Dar es Salaam. Data was collected from eight lecturers teaching first year students in the department of Political Science and Public Administration (PSPA) and Sociology and Social Anthropology (SSA). The objective of the study was to identify, describe, document and analyze the types of code-switching that lecturers used during lecturers using discourse approach. The findings revealed that lecturers used inter- and intra-sentential code-switch for phatic communications; to engage with students, to translate concept, to explain, to manage students' behaviour, and to advise or encourage students.

Another study was conducted by Rahmat, Arepin, Mohd Yunos and Syed Abdul Rahman (2017) was done to investigate whether code-switching is a catalyst or hindrance to communication. The quantitative study investigated the prevalence of code-switching among students. The instrument used is a questionnaire and it is used to explore the categories and functions of code-switching among learners. The study also looked into the reasons for code-switching given by the learners. Results of the study indicated that learners were learning language code-switch more than learners studying engineering thus revealing perhaps speakers from different streams differ in their use of code-switch.

The study by Itemizah, Ibnain, and Sha'fout (2017) investigated the most common types and functions of code-switching used by teachers in foreign language classes at the Palestine Ahliya University College (PAUC). The study was done to find out to what extent teachers code-switch in TEFL classrooms. The study was also done to find out the main types of code-switching observed in the TEFL classes. The study looked into the language functions that code-switch served. Finally, the study explored the language categories identified for the code-switches used by TEFL teachers. The findings revealed experienced teachers who wanted to teach grammatical rules often code-switch to buffer the concentration effect of rules presentation in class. The results also showed that teachers code-switched when explaining grammatical rules. They also code-switched to present new concepts and encourage students to participate in the class activities.

In addition to that, a study by Malulloluwa (2013) explored the use of code-switching in the second language classroom. The instruments used were audio recording of the class, interviews, and also non-participant observations. Findings showed that experienced teachers used L1 to make communicative effective. Teachers used code-switching for interactional, pedagogical and administrative reasons in the class. The teachers showed a positive attitude towards the use of L1. Code-switching is used as a compensatory strategy by teachers to communicate with learners with low L2 proficiency. Teachers also code-switch to create a positive classroom environment.

3. Material and Methods

85 respondents participated in this quantitative survey. They were lecturers teaching in a public university. They were from six faculties; applied sciences, computer and mathematical sciences, art and design, academy of language studies, accountancy and also business management.

The instrument used is a 5-point likert scale survey. Section A is about the respondents' demographic profiles. Section B looks at categories of code-switching (2 items), section C (7 items) looks at the functions and section D looks at reasons for code-switching (13 items). Data is collected through a google form. Lecturers from different faculties mean scores, -text and one way-ANOVA.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

This section reports the findings based on research questions.

4.2 Answer to RQ 1: Is there any significant difference in code-switching across age and teaching experience of teachers?

A. Categories of Code Switching

Table 1: Mean statistic score by group of age

	n	Mean	SD
18-30	8	4.69	2.17
31-40	32	5.16	1.79
41-50	32	4.89	1.87
51-60	13	5.88	1.89
Total	85	5.12	1.87

A one-way ANOVA between groups was performed to explore whether there is a significant difference in the categories of code switching among lecturers from different age groups. Lecturers were categorised into four different age groups which are 18-30, 31-40, 41-50 and 51-60. The mean statistic scored by the age group composition presented is in Table 1. The table revealed that lecturers between the age group 51-60 had the highest mean.

Table 2: One-Way ANOVA on categories of code switching by group of age

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	10.821	3	3.607	1.030	.384
Within groups	283.632	81	3.502		
Total	294.453	84			

The one way ANOVA result in Table 2 indicates that there was no statistically significant difference at the $p < .05$ level in the mean difficulties in categories of code switching for the four group of age, $F(3, 81) = 1.030$, $p = .384$. The effect size calculated using eta squared, was 0.04. This indicates that there is a small difference in mean difficulties in categories of code switching between groups. Although there is no evidence of past studies to show the increase use of code-switch with the increase of teachers' age; however, the study by Itemizah, Ibnain, and Sha'fout (2017) reported that more experienced teachers sometimes resort to code-switching when it comes to explaining rules.

B. Functions of Code Switching

Table 3: Mean statistic score by group of age

	n	Mean	SD
18-30	8	20.09	6.69
31-40	32	21.05	4.77
41-50	32	20.15	4.84
51-60	13	23.68	4.55
Total	85	21.02	5.02

A one-way ANOVA between groups was performed to explore whether there were differences in functions of code switching on lecturers from different group of age. Lecturers were compared by four different age groups which are 18-30, 31-40, 41-50 and 51-60. The mean statistic score by lecturers group of age composition presented in Table 3. Lecturers in the age group of 51-60 showed the highest mean for functions of code-switching.

Table 4: One-Way ANOVA on functions of code switching by group of age

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	123.409	3	41.136	1.673	.179
Within groups	1991.891	81	24.591		
Total	2115.300	84			

The one way ANOVA result in Table 4 indicates that there was no statistically significant difference at the $p < .05$ level in the mean difficulties in functions of code switching for the four age groups; $F(3, 81) = 1.673$, $p = .179$. The effect size was calculated using eta squared, and was found to be 0.06. This indicates that there was a medium difference in mean difficulties in functions of code switching between groups. Teachers of different ages use code-switch for different reasons. It was also reported by Kow (2003; and Then & Ting, (2009) that the function of code-switch differ across age.

C. Reasons for Code Switching

Table 5: Mean statistic score by group of age

	n	Mean	SD
18-30	8	35.46	11.55
31-40	32	35.87	7.26
41-50	32	34.14	7.48
51-60	13	37.97	5.70
Total	85	35.50	7.59

A one-way ANOVA between groups was performed to explore whether there were differences in the reasons for code switching on lecturers from different age groups. Lecturers were compared by four different age groups which are; 18-30, 31-40, 41-50 and 51-60. The mean statistic score by lecturers group of age composition presented in Table 5. Again, lecturers aged 51-60 were reported to have the highest mean for reasons for code-switch.

Table 6: Robust tests of equality of mean on reasons for code switching on lecturers from different group of age

	Statistic^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Welch	1.094	3	24.191	.371

The test for homogeneity of variance is shown in Table 6 and was found to be not significant $F(3,81) = .82$ $p < .05$ indicating that this assumption of variance was not assumed. Robust tests of equality of mean were referred to and the result is shown as in Table 6. There was no significant difference on reasons for code switching on lecturers from different age groups

4.2.1 Teaching Experience

A. Categories of Code Switching

Table 7: Mean statistic score by group of teaching experience

	n	Mean	SD
2 -5 years	16	4.41	1.68
6-10 years	21	5.26	2.07
11 years and above	48	5.30	1.82
Total	85	5.12	1.87

A one-way ANOVA between groups was performed to explore whether there were different in categories of code switching on lecturers from different teaching experience. Lecturers compared by three different group of teaching experience which is 2-5 years, 6-10 years, and 11 years above. The mean statistic score by lecturers in teaching experience composition presented in Table 7.

Table 8: One-Way ANOVA on categories of code switching by teaching experience

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	10.164	2	5.082	1.466	.237
Within groups	284.289	82	3.467		
Total	294.453	84			

The one way ANOVA result in Table 8 indicates that there was no statistically significant difference at the $p < .05$ level in the mean difficulties in categories of code switching for the three group of teaching experience, $F(2, 82) = 1.466$, $p = .237$. The effect size calculated using eta squared, was 0.03. This indicates that there was small difference in mean difficulties in categories of code switching between groups.

B. Functions of Code Switching

Table 9: Mean statistic score by group of teaching experience

	n	Mean	SD
2 -5 years	16	19.81	4.64
6-10 years	21	20.99	6.08
11 years and above	48	21.44	4.66
Total	85	21.02	5.02

A one-way ANOVA between groups was performed to explore whether there were different in functions of code switching on lecturers from different group of teaching experience. Lecturers compared by three different group of teaching experience which is 2-5 years, 6-10 years and 11 years and above. The mean statistic score by lecturers' group of teaching experience composition presented in Table 9.

Table 10: One-Way ANOVA on functions of code switching by group of teaching experience

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	31.959	2	15.979	.629	.536
Within groups	2083.341	82	25.407		
Total	2115.300	84			

The one way ANOVA result in Table 2 indicates that there was no statistically significant difference at the $p < .05$ level in the mean difficulties in functions of code switching for the three group of teaching experience, $F(2, 82) = .629$, $p = .536$. The effect size calculated using eta squared, was 0.01. This indicates that there was small difference in mean difficulties in functions of code switching between groups. The study by Malulloluwa (2013) indicated that experienced teachers sometimes code-switch to serve pedagogical functions.

C. Reasons for Code Switching

Table 11: Mean statistic score by group of teaching experience

	n	Mean	SD
2-5 years	16	32.56	7.26
6-10 years	21	37.24	8.65
11 years and above	48	35.73	7.06
Total	85	35.50	7.59

A one-way ANOVA between groups was performed to explore whether there were different in reasons for code switching on lecturers from different group of teaching experience. Lecturers compared by three different group of teaching experience which is 2-5 years, 6-10 years, and 11 years and above. The mean statistic score by lecturer' group of teaching experience composition presented in Table 11. Teachers with 6-10 years experience (more experienced than the ones who served 2-5 years) indicated higher tendency to code-switch. This finding is in accordance with the study by Malulloluwa (2013) indicated that more experienced used code-switching for interactional and organizational reasons.

Table 12: One-Way ANOVA on reasons for code switching by group of teaching experience

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	204.440	2	102.220	1.809	.170
Within groups	4632.478	82	56.494		
Total	4836.917	84			

The one way ANOVA result in Table 12 indicates that there was no statistically significant difference at the $p < .05$ level in the mean difficulties in reasons for code switching for the three group of teaching experience, $F(2, 82) = 1.809$, $p = .170$. The effect size calculated using eta squared, was 0.04. This indicates that there was small difference in mean difficulties in reasons for code switching between groups. Teachers were also reported to code-switch for the three groups of teaching experiences.

4.3 Answer to RQ 2: Is there any significant difference in code-switching among teachers across faculties?

A. Categories of Code Switching

Table 13: Mean statistic score by faculty

	n	Mean	SD
Applied Sciences	3	5.17	2.31
Computer and Mathematical Sciences	2	5.00	2.12
Art and Design	2	7.50	0.01
Academy of Language Studies (APB)	68	5.00	1.89
Accountancy	3	5.50	2.65
Business and Management	7	5.50	1.41
Total	85	5.12	1.87

A one-way ANOVA between groups was performed to explore whether there were different in categories of code switching on lecturers from different faculty. Lecturers compared by six different faculty which is Applied Sciences, Computer and Mathematical Sciences, Art and Design, Academy of Language Studies (APB), Accountancy, and Business and Management. The mean statistic score by lecturers group of faculty composition presented in Table 1.

Table 14: One-Way ANOVA on categories of code switching by faculty

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	13.786	5	2.757	.776	.570
Within groups	280.667	79	3.553		
Total	294.453	84			

The one way ANOVA result in Table 14 indicates that there was no statistically significant difference at the $p < .05$ level in the mean difficulties in categories of code switching for the six group of faculty, $F(5, 79) = .776, p = .570$. The effect size calculated using eta squared, was 0.04. This indicates that there was small difference in mean difficulties in categories of code switching between groups.

B. Functions of Code Switching

Table 15: Mean statistic score by group of faculty

	n	Mean	SD
Applied Sciences	3	23.00	4.58
Computer and Mathematical Sciences	2	21.43	0.01
Art and Design	2	23.36	5.96
Academy of Language Studies (APB)	68	20.91	5.18
Accountancy	3	18.00	5.05
Business and Management	7	21.76	4.74
Total	85	21.02	5.02

A one-way ANOVA between groups was performed to explore whether there were different in functions of code switching on lecturers from different faculty. Lecturers compared by six different faculty which is Applied Sciences, Computer and Mathematical Sciences, Art and Design, Academy of Language Studies (APB), Accountancy, and Business and Management. The mean statistic score by lecturers' group of faculty composition presented in Table 15. The highest mean for functions of code-switch is from Applied Sciences. The study by Malulloluwa (2013) reported teachers sometimes code-switch for pedagogical purposes. This is especially so for content lecturers to need to make sure students understand terms and definitions in their L1.

Table 15: One-Way ANOVA on functions of code switching by faculty

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	54.93	5	10.986	.421	.833
Within groups	2060.372	79	26.081		
Total	2115.300	84			

The one way ANOVA result in Table 16 indicates that there was no statistically significant difference at the $p < .05$ level in the mean difficulties in functions of code switching for the six faculties, $F(5, 79) = .421$, $p = .833$. The effect size calculated using eta squared, was 0.03. This indicates that there was small difference in mean difficulties in functions of code switching between groups.

C. Reasons for Code Switching

Table 17: Mean statistic score by faculty

	n	Mean	SD
Applied Sciences	3	37.56	9.64
Computer and Mathematical Sciences	2	36.73	.71
Art and Design	2	34.19	1.36
Academy of Language Studies (APB)	68	35.30	7.70
Accountancy	3	34.18	12.61
Business and Management	7	37.23	7.25
Total	85	35.50	7.59

A one-way ANOVA between groups was performed to explore whether there were different in reasons for code switching on lecturers from different faculty. Lecturers compared by six different faculty which is Applied Sciences, Computer and Mathematical Sciences, Art and Design, Academy of Language Studies (APB), Accountancy, and Business and Management. The mean statistic score by lecturers' group of faculty composition presented in Table 17.

Table 18: One-Way ANOVA on reasons for code switching by faculty

Source	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	48.249	5	9.650	.159	.977
Within groups	4788.668	79	60.616		
Total	4836.917	84			

The one way ANOVA result in Table 18 indicates that there was no statistically significant difference at the $p < .05$ level in the mean difficulties in reasons for code switching for the six faculties, $F(5, 79) = .159$, $p = .977$. The effect size calculated using eta squared, was 0.01. This indicates that there was small difference in mean difficulties in reasons for code switching between groups.

4.4 Answer to RQ 3: How do the categories of code-switching influence classroom communication?

Figure 1: Categories of Code-Switching

Figure 1 above shows the findings for categories of code-switching overall. Lecturers were found to use more intrasentential (3.51) compared to intersentential (3.24). When lecturers use intrasentential, they would use L1 when they could not find English word in a sentence. On the other hand, lecturers use intersentential when they mixed L1 and English alternately from one sentence to another (Rahmat, Arepin, Mohd Yunos and Syed Abdul Rahman (2017).

4.5 Answer to RQ 4: How do the functions of code-switching influence classroom communication?

Figure 2: Functions of Code-Switching

Figure 2 presents the functions of code-switch. Interestingly, the highest mean is for “using Malay when they do not want the other person to join the discussion”. This is seen as a social function for code-switching. This is also supported by the study done by Mohamad Khalis and Mohd Shahril Firdaus (2018) who reported that code-switching functions to show belonging to a certain group.

4.6 Answer to RQ 5: How to reasons for code-switching influence classroom communication?

Figure 3: Reasons for Code-Switching

Figure 3 presents the reasons for code-switch among lecturers. Interestingly, the highest mean showed that code-switching is used to bid farewell (3.6) as well as greet people (3.29). The study by Shartiely (2016) also found that code-switching is used by teachers as a form of phatic communication. This means L1 is needed for routine communications like greetings and goodbyes.

5. Conclusion

This study set out to determine the use of inter-sentential code switching among lecturers of a public university in Malaysia, where English is mainly the medium of instruction for many core courses at the university. The findings of this study reveal that the lecturers were found to use more intrasentential compared to intersentential code-switching. Results of this investigation also show that the significant difference in code-switching among teachers across age, experience, and faculties is very minimal. One of the more significant findings to emerge from this study is that the higher age group and more experienced lecturers tend to code-switch more. These lecturers are reported to use intrasentential code-switching for the purpose of interactional,

pedagogical and administrative as there is a need to make students feel comfortable, to understand the subject matter better, to take instructions clearly. Code-switching is also used when English words are not found in the sentence. As suggested by Kustati (2014) teachers' code-switching is significantly associated with students' learning success and code-switching is used to clarify certain issues making them more comprehensible to low –proficiency students. Findings of this research also support the claim of Malulloluwa (2013) that code switching is used to make communicative effective. On the basis of the findings of this study, it is recommended that further research should be carried out on coming up with a standardize measurement of evaluating the functions and reasons of code-switching among the teachers and students. According to Low (2016), as code-switching is an uncontainable phenomenon in a multilingual post-colonial society like Malaysia, the potential of code-switching in classroom teaching as a communicative resource needs to be recognized by the academic authorities.

About the Author(s)

Noor Hanim Rahmat (PhD) is an associate professor teaching ESL at Akademi Pengajian Bahasa at Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah ALam, Selangor, Malaysia for the past 25 years. Her research interests include academic writing, reading, language proficiency, educational psychology and teacher training.

Noor Ahnis Othman (PhD) is the deputy dean for research, industry, community and alumni network at the Akademi Pengajian Bahasa, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam. She has taught in the university for almost 30 years. Besides research writing, she is also an active member in non-profit organization for underprivileged children.

Norseha Unin (PhD) has taught English at Universiti Teknologi MARA in Sarawak for almost 30 years. She did her BA in English and M.Ed. at Northern Illinois University before joining the English Department in 1990. She holds a PhD from Michigan State University. Besides teaching English courses at undergraduate level, she also supervises masters and doctoral students. She has presented papers at conferences both home and abroad, and published articles in various journals. Over the last five years she has become involved with PPSEAWA (Pan-Pacific Southeast Asian Women Association) in conducting English Enrichment programs for school kids in rural areas. She is currently the Vice Chairperson for PPSEAWA (Sarawak Chapter).

References

- Ahmad, Badrul & Jusoff, Kamaruzaman. (2009). Teachers' Code-Switching in Classroom Instructions for Low English Proficient Learners. *English Language Teaching*. 2. 10.5539/elt.vol.2 no.2 p49.
- Bhatia, T. K., & Ritchie, W. C. (2004). Social and Psychological Factors in Language Mixing. In W. C. Ritchie and T. K. Bhatia (eds.), *Handbook of Bilingualism* (pp.336-352). Blackwell Publishing.

- Chen, M. M. A. B., & Maarof, N. (2017). Code switching among Malaysian primary school teachers in teaching English as a second language. *Man in India*, 97(13), 31-39.
- Chen, David & Ting, Su-Hie. (2011). Code-switching in English and science classrooms: More than translation. *International Journal of Multilingualism*. 8. 299-323.
- Clyne, M. (2000). Constraints on code-switching: How universal are they? In Li, W . (Ed). *The bilingualism reader*. London: Routledge.
- Grosjean, F. (1982). *Life with two language. An introduction to bilingualism*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Itmeizah, M., Ibnian, S. S., and Sha'fout, M. (2017) Cod-Switching among Teachers of English Language Service Courses at PAUC: Types and Functions. *Asian Journal of Humanities and Social Studies*. Vol 5(4). Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319328771_Code-Switching_among_Teachers_of_English_Language_Service_Courses_at_PAUC_Types_and_Functions
- Kow, Y. C. (2003). Codeswitching for a purpose: Focus on preschool Malaysian children. *Multilingua*, 22, 59 - 77.
- Lee, H. L. J. (2010). Code switching in the Teaching of English as a second language to secondary school students. *Malaysian Journal of ELT Research*. Vol 6, 1-45. Retrieved August 8, 2018, from www.melta.org.my.
- Low, Suk May (2016) *The Effectiveness of Classroom Code-switching in Malaysian Science Classrooms*. PhD thesis, University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK.
- Makulloluwa, E. (2013) Code-Switching by Teachers in the Second Language Classroom. *International Journal of Arts & Sciences*, Vol 6(3).
- Mattsson, A & Burenhult-Mattsson, N. (1999). Code-switching in second language teaching of French. *Working Papers* 47: 59-72.
- Mohamad Khalil, S., Mohd Shahril Firda, M.S.Z. (2018) Inter-Sentential and Intra-Sentential Code-Switching in Parlimentary Debate. *International Journal of Modern Languages and Applied Linguistics*. Vol 2(2)
- Mokhtar, Mazlin M. (2015). Lecturers' and students' beliefs in code-switching: a Malaysian polytechnic context. *TEFLIN Journal*, Vol. 26, No. 1.
- Poplack, S. (ed.). (2000). *The English History of African American English*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Tay, M. W. J. (1989). Code switching and code mixing as a communicative strategy in multilingual discourse. *World Englishes*, 8(3), 407-417.
- Rahmat, N. H., Arepin, M., Mohd Yunos, D. R., and Syed Abdul Rahman, S. A. (2017) Code Switching among ESL Learners: Catalyse or Hindrance for Communication? Proceedings for 3rd International Conference on Advanced Research in Business and Social Sciences 2017 29th to 30th March, 2017 Aseania Resort & Spa Langkawi, Malaysia

- Sert, O. (2005). The functions of code switching in ELT classrooms. *The Internet TESL Journal*, XI(8). Retrieved August 7, 2018, from <http://iteslj.org/Articles/Sert-CodeSwitching.html>
- Shartiely, N. E. (2016) Code-Switching in University Classroom in Interaction: A Case Study of the University of Dar es Salam. *Stellenbosch Papers in Linguistic Plus*, Vol 49, pp 215-231. Retrieved from <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/splp/article/viewFile/151876/141472>
- Then, D. C. O., & Ting, S. H. (2009). Preliminary study of code-switching in English and Science secondary school classrooms in Malaysia. *Teaching of English as a Second or Foreign Language (TESL-Electronic Journal)*, 13(1), A3. Retrieved August 9, 2018, from <http://tesl-ej.org/ej49/a3.html>
- Torres, L. (1989). Code-mixing and borrowing in a New York Puerto Rican community; A cross-generational study. *World Englishes*, 8, 419-432.
- Kustati, M. (2014). An Analysis of Code-Mixing and Code-Switching in EFL Teaching of Cross Cultural Communication Context. *Al-Ta'lim Online Journal*, 21(3), 174-182. DOI: 10.15548/jt.v21i3.101
- Zentella, A. C. (1999). *Growing up bilingual*. Malden. MA: Blackwell.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions, and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of English Language Teaching shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).